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ABSTRACT

The overall objective of the EJP Soil project SIMPLE is to assess the impact policy changes and socioeconomic effects have on three ecosystem services of soils: yields, soil carbon storage and greenhouse gas mitigation.

WP6 aims to assess how land-use change is influenced by social, economic, political and biophysical factors and quantify the impact of the resulting ecological processes (caused by land-use intensification and extensification) on agricultural activities as well as ecosystem services of soil for different scenarios.

Regional scale assessment is based by using two approaches, representing Eastern Baltics, case of Latvia:

- 1) Influence of biophysical factors on different land use in landscape types of Latvia.
- 2) Land use change scenarios in former agricultural lands in marginal area in Eastern Baltics, case of Latvia.

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1. Introduction

The overall objective of the EJP Soil project SIMPLE is to assess the impact policy changes and socioeconomic effects have on three ecosystem services of soils: yields, soil carbon storage and greenhouse gas mitigation.

WP6 aims to assess how land-use change is influenced by social, economic, political and biophysical factors and quantify the impact of the resulting ecological processes (caused by land-use intensification and extensification) on agricultural activities as well as ecosystem services of soil for different scenarios.

Since 2000, changes in total agricultural lands in Europe are marginal, as a slight increase in croplands is accompanied by a slight decrease in permanent meadows and pastures. In Europe, agricultural lands have a bigger share of croplands to meadows and pastures; within croplands, the share of herbaceous crops increased.

European scale scenarios developed in WP2 are analysed and complemented with regional scale studies from the Baltic States that experience significant land-use change.

This report introduces regional scale assessment of the impact of driving factors for land use change processes, agricultural activities and related changes in soil properties and provision of ecosystem services is based by using two approaches, representing land use driving factors in Eastern Baltics, case of Latvia by preparation of two articles (related to chapter 2 and chapter 3).

The report is divided into 4 main sections. The first one is being this introduction section. A literature review (Deliverable 6.2.) on land use change reveals influencing driving forces, factors and processes, as well as its spatial relationships that reflects intensification and extensification of agricultural land management.

Chapter 2 reveals regional assessment of the biophysical factors influence on different land use and agricultural management (intensification and extensification) in landscape types of Latvia: upland mosaic landscape, plain agriculture landscape, polder agriculture landscape, undulated topography agriculture landscape. In this assessment, the impact of the Europe Green Deal and CAP policy on the processes of agricultural management (intensification and extensification) is characterized by the change of land use in the period from 2014 to 2024. During this period, there are different trends in each landscape type.

Chapter 3 reflects land use change scenarios in former agricultural lands of a marginal area in the Eastern Baltics, case of Latvia, focusing on different land use change patterns and the changes in soil properties driven by secondary succession across various land use types. The research focuses on the

transition of grassland and arable land to forest cover, largely driven by the process of land use intensification, natural afforestation, and agricultural abandonment. It also examines the impacts of these transitions on soil properties, including pH, total carbon and nitrogen content, and nutrient availability.

Chapter 4 contains recommendations section revealing main outcomes from the chapter 2 and chapter 3 in relation to agricultural management in case study of Eastern Baltics, Latvia.

2. Influence of biophysical factors on different land use in landscape types of Latvia

2.1. Introduction

Since the end of the Second World War, Europe has experienced two major trends in agriculture: intensification and the marginalization of agricultural land (Brouwer, 2006; van der Sluis et al., 2016). Land use intensity increased through higher agricultural outputs, that was achieved through cropland expansion or increased crop production per unit area (García et al., 2020; Meyfroidt et al., 2018; Thomson et al., 2019). Globally, intensification also affected grasslands, often it went through ploughing and conversion to arable lands (Oenema et al., 2014). These changes threaten several ecosystem services (ES), with grasslands playing a crucial role in providing ES within agricultural landscapes (Allan et al., 2015; Schils et al., 2022). Permanent grasslands, in particular, are vital for ES provision. However, the decline in permanent grassland areas has continued, and due to land use change, it exists nowadays (Schils et al., 2022). Studies in different countries show that in the most productive soils, permanent grasslands undergo transformation to arable land (Kitczak et al., 2023), but in the least productive areas, grasslands tend to overgrow by trees naturally or are transformed due to afforestation (Kitczak et al., 2023; Vanwambeke et al., 2012; Vinogradovs et al., 2018).

Abandonment of agriculture is the opposite process, but it is also relevant to Europe's agricultural landscape. Specifically, it is a critical issue in Europe, particularly visible in socialist Central and Eastern European countries, mountain and Mediterranean regions (Leal Filho et al., 2017). The course of land use is determined by various driving forces: political, economic, cultural, technological, and natural/s by various driving forces: political, economic, cultural, technological, and natural/spatial driving forces (2016). Scholars highlight the significance of biophysical characteristics, such as soil fertility, which affects both intensification and extensification (Opršal et al., 2016; Pazúr et al., 2024; Prishchepov et al., 2011).

Dynamics and trends in land use intensification and extensification are also shaped by political influence. Government policies, including zoning laws and environmental regulations, have been

identified as crucial in directing land use practices (Hellwig et al., 2019). The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) is a key EU land management policy and a central driver for agricultural land management. In the future, implementation of the Green Deal will push peat soils towards political climate mitigation activities (Buschmann et al., 2020), because low costs and high GHG mitigation potential put peat soil in focus compared to the other possible GHG mitigation in the agricultural sector (Krimly et al., 2016; Rebhann et al., 2016; Tanneberger et al., 2021). CAP for 2023 – 2027 has more enhanced GAECs that are relevant for soil protection, f.e, peatland protection, reduction of soil erosion through tillage management, buffer strips, cover crops, etc. (Panagos et al., 2022). Scholars stress that currently, at the EU level, peatland management is one of the most controversial topics as CAP counteracts climate targets as direct payments promote unsustainable peatland management (Chen et al., 2024). These abovementioned statements and trends in land use management determined the selection criteria for study territories; we included areas where some of the agricultural lands were located on peatlands.

Previous studies In Latvia focused on topics related to land abandonment. These studies describe the abandonment process and driving forces in the local level (Nikodemus et al., 2005; Ruskule et al., 2012; Vanwambeke et al., 2012; Vinogradovs et al., 2018) and impact of soil properties (Afanasjeva et al., 2024; Kukuļs et al., 2019; Nikodemus et al., 2020) and EU direct payment impact on land use (Nikodemus et al., 2010). Most of these studies were conducted before the implementation of the EU Green Deal and focused on processes in upland landscapes. Studies show that soil factors and topography are the main driving factors determining changes in land use. However, having information from different landscapes is crucial to make data driver decisions on land lease intensification and extensification.

The study **aimed** to identify the role of the biophysical factors in land use intensification and extensification in different predominant landscapes in Latvia. The **tasks** for the study were defined as:

- To identify the biophysical factors on different landscapes and its use;
- To characterise EU Green Deal impact on land use types in different landscapes;
- To identify trends in peat soil use in different landscapes.'

2.2. Methodology

To investigate the agricultural landscape characteristics across different regions in Latvia, three case study areas, each with a 5x5 km square grid, were selected from four typical agricultural landscape types: upland mosaic landscape, plain agriculture landscape, polder agriculture landscape, and undulated topography agriculture landscape (Figure 2.1).

Detailed maps depicting land use and soil information were developed by integrating data from multiple sources, including soils survey maps (Ministry of Agriculture, L., 2020), drainage system maps (Department of Land Amelioration, M. of A. E. R. of L., 2018), IACS-LPIS data from Rural Support Service. For each of the selected case study areas, the agricultural land was overlaid with a 100x100 m grid, where data layers corresponding to several key attributes were assigned to a spatial database. These attributes included: (i) agricultural land use in 2024 (categorized as arable, grassland, or abandoned), (ii) agricultural land use in 2014 (also categorized as arable, grassland, or abandoned), (iii) soil type (classified into mineral soil, shallow peat soil (peat layer 30 – 60 cm), and deep peat soil (peat layer > 60 cm)), (iv) drainage system type (categorized as closed, open, or none), and (v) land quality value (represented by points). This spatial data framework resulted in the creation of 16,488 data points for subsequent analysis, allowing for a comprehensive evaluation of the relationships between land use, soil properties, and agricultural practices over time.

The Sankey diagrams illustrating land use changes between 2014 and 2024 were produced using Python with the Plotly library. The dataset used for the analysis contained land use classifications for two-time points (2014 and 2024, IACS LPIS data, Rural Support Service). Transitions between these classifications were calculated by grouping the data to identify the number of occurrences for each land use type in 2014 transitioning to a corresponding type in 2024. These transitions were then visualized in a Sankey diagram, with land use types from 2014 displayed on the left side and those from 2024 on the right side.

To estimate the land-use influencing biophysical factors (land quality, shallow peat soils, deep peat soils, open drainage, no drainage) on the land use types (arable land, grasslands, abandoned land) in 2024 - autologistic binary regression (ABR) models were constructed as implemented in software R 3.4.0. (R Core Team, 2017).

Figure 2.1. Locations of studied landscape types of land use changes between 2014 and 2024 of arable land, grassland and abandoned land

2.3. Results

2.3.1 Characterization of the study areas

The defined soil type proportion differs in the studied areas within different landscapes (Table 2.1.). Mineral soil is the most dominant soil type within all studied agricultural landscapes. Peat soils, especially deep peat soils, make a higher proportion in the upland mosaic landscapes, as peat soil is formed in the valleys.

Studied landscapes differ more in terms of land-use type. Upland mosaic landscapes have higher intensification processes as approximately 1/3 of the total agricultural area is abandoned from agricultural landscapes. Also, a relatively high proportion of grasslands (35%) indicates that intensive farming through crop production isn't the main activity within those areas. As data on grassland management are absent, we can't precisely indicate the intensity of the management within the grasslands. In the other studied landscapes, as the topography is more suitable for more intensive management, t.i. soil tillage, arable land is the dominant land use type in the agricultural areas; the proportion exceeds 62% of the total agricultural area. Grassland proportions are relatively similar and make 15.5% up to 19.3%. In addition, areas which have undergone significant land amelioration procedures – polders, have – high intensification, as land abandonment in these areas is the lowest.

Table 2.1.

Proportions (%) of land use, soil classes and drainage conditions within studied agricultural landscapes

Landscape type Parameter	Soil conditions			Land use type			Land drainage conditions		
	Deep peat soil (DPS)	Mineral soil (MS)	Shallow peat soil (SPS)	Arable (AR)	Grassland (GL)	Abandoned (AB)	Closed Drainage	Open Drainage	Not drained
<i>Upland mosaic landscape type</i>	16.0	83.1	0.9	31.8	35	33.2	86.7	2.7	10.6
<i>Plain agriculture landscape type</i>	12.5	84.3	3.2	66.5	15.5	18.0	90.7	4.4	4.9
<i>Polder agriculture landscape type</i>	13.4	84.1	2.5	71.2	18.5	10.3	90.0	4.8	5.2
<i>Undulated topography agriculture landscape type</i>	5.9	93.1	1.0	62.0	19.3	18.7	93.8	1.9	4.3

Analysis of the drainage status reveals that the studied landscapes have undergone vast drainage programs; therefore, from a historical perspective, those territories were shaped for intensive agricultural use. In plain landscapes, polder landscapes, and undulated topography landscapes, the proportion of the territories with closed drainage systems is more than 90%, and less than 5.2% of the total area isn't drained. In the Upland mosaic landscapes, the share of the undrained area reaches 10.6%.

Table 2.2.

Land quality (balls) characteristics within studied agricultural landscapes

Landscape type	Upland mosaic landscape type	Plain agriculture landscape type	Polder agriculture landscape type	Undulated topography agriculture landscape type
Mean	34	42	40	42
Median	35	45	40	45
STD	9	9	6	8
RANGE	55	55	45	50

Land quality data – the concept that represents integrated soil fertility evaluation and is based on soil texture, type, topography and stoniness (Boruks et al., 2001) – within the most intensively managed and the most productive areas of Latvia is over 70. In the studied territories, land quality data sums up the overall situation. Upland mosaic landscapes are the least suitable for agricultural production as mean and median values are lower than other studied landscapes.

2.3.2 Land use change

In this regional assessment, the impact of the Europe Green Deal and CAP policy on the processes of agricultural management (intensification and extensification) is characterized by the change of land use in the period from 2014 to 2024. During this period, there are different trends in each landscape type.

2.3.2.1 Land use changes in different landscape types

Plain agriculture landscape type

Plain agriculture landscape type largest area is occupied by arable lands and its total area within time period from 2014 until 2024 is slightly increased (Fig. 2.2.). Area of abandoned agricultural land has slightly decreased (Fig. 2.2.). In general, when evaluating the changes in the land use structure over the 11-year period, plain landscape type is not significant.

Figure 2.2. Proportions (%) of land use in plain agriculture landscape type in 2014 and 2024 between arable land, grassland and abandoned land

Polder agriculture landscape type

The polder agriculture landscapes are also dominated by arable land, which occupied 62.3% of agricultural land in 2014, and 69.7% in 2024. (Fig. 2.3.). This indicates an increase in the intensification of land use mainly at the portion of grasslands and abandoned agricultural lands, the areas of which have decreased in the studied areas.

Figure 2.3. Proportions (%) of land use in polder agriculture landscape type in 2014 and 2024 between arable land, grassland and abandoned land

Undulated topography agriculture landscape type

Undulated topography agriculture landscape type is also dominated by arable land (Fig. 2.4.), however in comparison to the previously analysed landscapes, the process of extensification can be observed in this undulated topography agriculture landscape, as the area of arable land has significantly decreased. Part of the arable land has been transformed into grassland and thus the grassland area has significantly increased in the landscape.

Figure 2.4. Proportions (%) of land use in undulated topography agriculture landscape type in 2014 and 2024 between arable land, grassland and abandoned land

Upland mosaic landscape type

In the upland landscape type, where relatively large areas of agricultural land (40.8%) were occupied abandoned agricultural land in 2014, - a decrease in these areas can be observed at the portion of arable land and grasslands (Fig. 2.5.). The areas of arable land and grasslands have slightly increased in this landscape, but the mentioned processes are not unambiguous, as the detected changes are not statistically significant.

The decrease in the area of abandoned agricultural lands on the one hand indicates the intensification process, however on the other hand, the return of land to agricultural circulation indicates the interest of farmers to receive CAP payments. In Latvia, CAP payments, especially in biologically diverse grasslands, have significantly increased compared to the previous planning period and the current period.

Figure 2.5. Proportions (%) of land use in upland mosaic landscape type in 2014 and 2024 between arable land, grassland and abandoned land

In general, the directions of land use change vary depending on the type of landscape. The implementation of eco-schemes in CAP payments in relation to land use change can be evaluated ambiguously. On the one hand, this regional assessment reveals an increase in grassland areas in upland mosaic landscape type and undulated topography agriculture landscape type, however on the other hand, arable land areas in plain agriculture landscape type and polder agricultural landscape type have increased. In order to be able to better explain the mentioned relationships, it is recommended to perform an analysis of land use changes at the farm level.

2.3.2.2. Land use influencing biophysical factors in 2024

The explained variance of the Autologistic binary regression (ABR) model for arable land was 53% (Table 2.3.). Analysis of the whole dataset from all studied sites indicates that the distribution of arable land is closely related to soil productivity (positive correlation, $p < 0.001$) (Table 2.3.).

The second most significant driving force is drainage. Territories with closed drainage are highly likely to be used as arable lands. Still, territories that are open or without drainage will likely be used as grasslands or abandoned. Also, there is the likely outcome that territories with deep peat soils won't be used as arable land. Amelioration and drainage, executed during the Soviet occupation, also tended to the massivisation of the fields and agricultural lands.

This fact leads us to conclude that arable lands within different landscapes are related to the vast ameliorated and productive territories, which is especially typical for the plain agriculture landscape, polder agriculture landscapes and undulated topography landscapes.

Table 2.3.

Results of ABR model (variables with significance level $p < 0.001$ displayed in bold).
Overall explained variance of the ABR model was 53% for arable land.

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z	P> z	Odds Ratio
Land quality	0.04	0.00	12.59	<0.001	1.04
Shallow peat soils	-0.08	0.18	-0.42	0.67	0.93
Deep peat soils	-0.29	0.08	-3.73	<0.001	0.75
Open drainage	-1.04	0.13	-8.11	<0.001	0.35
No drainage	-0.54	0.10	-5.27	<0.001	0.58

The explained variance of the ABR model for arable land was 50% (Table 2.4.). The main biophysical driving force for grasslands is predominated by distribution of deep peat soil. Drainage and land quality do not appear statistically significant. Peat soil is also a substantial factor for grassland, as it increases the possibility of occurrence (Tab. 2.4.).

Table 2.4.

Results of ABR model (variables with significance level $p < 0.001$ displayed in bold).
Overall explained variance of the ABR model was 50% for grasslands.

Variable	Coefficient	Std Err	z	P> z	Odds Ratio
Land quality	-0.002	0.004	-0.69	<0.001	0.99
Shallow peat soils	0.09	0.18	0.48	0.63	1.09
Deep peat soils	0.21	0.08	2.42	0.01	1.23
Open drainage	-0.25	0.15	-1.61	0.10	0.77
No drainage	-0.006	0.11	-0.05	0.95	0.99

The explained variance of the ABR model for arable land was 34% (Table 2.5.). In abandoned lands, the main biophysical factors are land quality (the less, the higher possibility to abandonment process and extensification of agricultural management), and drainage (if not, the higher possibility to be abandoned).

Undrained soils and shallow peat soils also contribute to the abandonment process (Tab. 2.5.).

Table 2.5.

Results of ABR model (variables with significance level $p < 0.001$ displayed in bold).
Overall explained variance of the ABR model was 34% for abandoned land.

Variable	Coefficient	Std Err	z	P> z	Odds Ratio
Land quality	-0.04	0.00	-14.69	<0.001	0.96
Shallow peat soils	-0.15	0.18	-0.84	0.40	0.86
Deep peat soils	0.10	0.08	1.35	0.17	1.11
Open drainage	1.13	0.11	9.98	<0.001	3.08
No drainage	0.53	0.09	5.68	<0.001	1.70

This study shows that similarly to earlier investigations (Vinogradovs et al., 2018, Vanwambeke et al., 2012), despite the change in EU agriculture policy and CAP payment priorities, the most important driving forces of biophysical factors are soil fertility or land quality and drainage of area. Peat soils do not significantly affect land use in most cases, only the case when arable lands could not be cultivated on deep peat soils.

2.3.2.3. Crop rotation and land-use changes on agricultural peat soils in different landscape types

On peat soils, crop rotation in arable lands and land-use dynamics in the agricultural lands as a whole differ between periods 2014-2024 if we compare all landscape types (Table 2.6.). Land on peat soils in plain agricultural landscapes in 2014 was mainly used as grasslands (52.9% of the total peat soil area). However, further intensification has led to a reduction in grassland areas. In 2024, grasslands made only 28.8%, and arable lands were the dominant land use type on peat soils, mainly used for wheat production. During the studied period, the area of abandoned lands also increased. Due to CAP funding rules regulating crop rotation in arable lands, the number of types of cultivated crops on peat soils has increased, and peas and red clover are grown in small areas. These changes have led to more intensive use of the peat soils in agriculture.

Opposite trends were in the undulated topography agricultural landscapes. During the studied period, grassland proportion significantly increased in the peat soil areas, but arable lands decreased. Arable peat soils in 2014 were mainly used for barley production (67.5% of the total area), but in studies, peat soils were not used for barley production; peat soils were dominated by wheat crops (64.4% of the total area). These changes are probably caused by current crop profitability in represented years. CAP policies may have caused an increase in total fallow area; in 2024, data shows fallow areas have a considerable proportion of the total arable peat soils. Overall, peat soil in the undulated topography agriculture landscape has tendencies towards extensification.

Within the studied period, peat soil land intensification was evident in the polder agriculture landscapes (Table 2.6.), a significant increase in arable land area. In both years, wheat was the dominant crop cultivated. A decrease in grassland and abandoned land areas also indicates the intensification of peat soils. On the one hand, these tendencies contradict the EU Green Deal. Still, crop rotation, greening, and cultivation of peas indicate that land management is by current EU agricultural policies.

Table 2.6.

Land-use (%) in peat soils in different landscape types in 2014 and 2024. Arable land further divided into crop types.

Landscape type	Land-use type	2014	2024
Plain agriculture landscape type	Abandoned	18.3	24.8
	Grassland	52.9	28.8
	Arable	28.8	46.4
	Oats	0	13.4
	Wheat	30.8	46.5
	Rape	0	17.1
	Buckwheat	23.6	10.3
	Red clover	0	1.2
	Peas	0	2.2
	Energy crops	31.8	0
	Fallow	1	4.9
Other	12.8	4.4	
Polder agriculture landscape type	Abandoned	15.2	9.0
	Grassland	58.0	34.5
	Arable	26.7	56.5
	Oats	0.0	5.4
	Wheat	64.4	52.2
	Barley	8.0	8.4
	Rape	0.0	8.2
	Rye	0.0	6.5
	Peas	0.0	7.8
	Potatoes	7.1	5.6
	Fallow	1.5	4.6
Other	4.1	1.3	
Undulated topography agriculture landscape type	Abandoned	28.6	29.2
	Grassland	26.6	42.9
	Arable	44.8	28.0
	Oats	4.8	0
	Wheat	0	64.4
	Barley	67.5	0
	Rye	13.3	11.5
	Energy crops	14.5	0
	Fallow	0.0	18.8
	Other	0.0	5.2
Upland mosaic landscape type	Abandoned	40.1	36,5
	Grassland	32.0	27,6
	Arable	27.8	36,0
	Oats	18.0	17.3
	Wheat	21.8	26.6
	Barley	10.5	8.9
	Rape	0.0	7.0
	Rye	30.8	12.1
	Triticale	8.3	0
	Red clover	0	8.4
	Peas	0	10.3
Other	0	9.3	

There are diverse spatial mosaics within peat soil areas in upland mosaic-type landscapes in 2014; grasslands and abandoned lands are the dominant land use types. Arable lands are used for rye and wheat cultivation, and the share of these crops is 30.8% and 21.8%, respectively. In 2024, small intensification is evident as a slight increase in arable land area accompanies a decrease in grassland and abandoned areas. There is an increase in the wheat production area but a slight decrease in the rye production area. Also, in the arable lands on peat soils in upland mosaic-type landscapes, the diversity of crops increases. EU policy impact is evident as peas and red clover are part of the crop rotation (10.3% and 8.4% of the total peat soil area). Despite the goals of EU environmental policies - carbon emission reduction in agricultural lands and biodiversity protection, significant areas are tilled in studied areas and increases in arable land are evident in all landscape types. The Positive trend is an increase in crop diversity in crop rotation systems in plain agriculture type and polder agriculture type landscapes.

2.4. Conclusions

Study results show that intensification and extensification processes in Latvia are driven by landscape and soil productivity. In the plain and polder agricultural landscapes, land use tends to increase. As a result, grassland areas decreased, but arable land areas increased. In the undulated topography, agriculture and upland mosaic-type landscapes tend to be opposite; grassland areas tend to increase slightly. Results show that due to CAP payments in all landscapes, areas of abandoned land decrease. From the soil biophysical factors, land quality and drainage drive land-use trajectories.

In general, peat soil, including deep peat soil in most landscapes isn't a determining factor for land use, which shows that EU and state mechanisms do not reach a goal - to prevent peat soil use as arable land. At the same time, we must consider that since the end of land amelioration and soil mapping, more than 30 years have passed, and peat has undergone mineralisation and may not be classified as peat soils. Therefore, to implement the EU policies and land use sustainable management and reach defined goals, it is crucial to execute a new soil mapping process to have updated soil information on a national level (Nikodemus et al., 2024).

3. Land use change scenarios in former agricultural lands in marginal area in Eastern Baltics, case of Latvia

3.1. Introduction

European policies promoting afforestation aim to enhance carbon sequestration and biodiversity, contributing to global environmental goals (Abolina & Luzadis, 2015). Afforestation benefits include improved soil stability, water quality, carbon storage, and wildlife habitats (Plantinga & Wu, 2003; Vuichard et al., 2008), though it may conflict with food security. European forest cover has grown significantly over last century, this expansion is primarily attributed to the decline of agriculture and rural-to-urban population shifts, enabling both natural and artificial reforestation (Pichler et al., 2011), similar trend observed in Latvia, where forest area has markedly increased since the 1920s (Tērauds et al., 2008). According to data from the Rural Support Service, in 2024, approximately 9% (188 597 ha) of the total agricultural land was abandoned, with the trend most pronounced in Riga and Latgale region (The Rural Support Service of Latvia, n.d.). Farmland abandonment often occurs in marginal areas, raising conflicts between agricultural expansion and the environmental advantages of forest regeneration (Mantero et al., 2020; Murua et al., 2013). While restoring abandoned lands could boost food production, it involves substantial ecological and financial costs, depending on abandonment duration and vegetation succession (Beringer et al., 2011; Foley et al., 2011; Zahawi et al., 2014; Zheng et al., 2023). Natural succession transforming abandoned lands into forests can result in the loss of high-potential farmlands and grasslands (Burrascano et al., 2016), driven by factors like rural depopulation and economic shifts (Prishchepov et al., 2011; Rey Benayas et al., 2007). Soil quality remains crucial in land-use decisions, as fertile soils tend to be cultivated while poorer soils are abandoned (Bell et al., 2009; Jepsen et al., 2015). Although abandonment often affects low-quality land, productive farmland in Latvia has also been impacted (Stoate et al., 2009; Van Dijk et al., 2005). Research shows that broadleaf tree afforestation can enhance topsoil pH, organic carbon, nitrogen, and cation exchange capacity (Hübllová & Frouz, 2021; Morazzo et al., 2021; Segura et al., 2019), while coniferous trees may increase soil acidification and alter nutrient composition (Nikodemus et al., 2022). Previous studies have shown that, in some cases, nitrogen content in soils under *Alnus incana* stands on afforested agricultural land increases (Nikodemus et al., 2020). Additionally, after 15 years, natural afforestation with *Picea abies* significantly affects soil chemical properties and microbiological activity (Afanasjeva et al., 2024). Numerous studies have been conducted in the Vidzeme Upland; however, the present study focuses on the Latgale Upland, where soil formation conditions and bio-physical factors such as climate, topography, and soil properties differ (Nikodemus et al., 2018).

During the last few decades, significant agricultural land abandonment in Latvia has been influenced by socioeconomic, political, and soil quality factors, as soil properties play a crucial role in vegetation development. In the process of agricultural land extensification – abandonment and afforestation – soil factors are particularly important. However, there remains a gap in understanding the spatial relationships between soil properties and land use changes following agricultural land abandonment, which is essential for informed land management decisions. Therefore, the current case study aims to investigate

- (1) different scenarios of land use change in marginal area and
- (2) influence of soil factors, soil properties and topography on land-use change in marginal upland landscape.
- (3) soil properties after extensification and related land-use changes.

3.2. Methodology

3.2.1. Case study site description

The study area is located in the Eastern Baltics (Fig.3.1.a), specifically in the Latgale Upland, a marginal region characterized by slightly undulating topography. The research was conducted on a 318-hectare site selected due to significant land use changes. Historically used as arable land and grassland, the area has undergone substantial transformation over the past 60 years (1954-2014), with forest cover increasing significantly while arable land and grassland have diminished. Most abandoned sites have become overgrown with species such as *Alnus incana*, *Salix caprea*, *Betula pendula*, *Populus tremula*, and *Picea abies* (Fig.3.1.b).

Fig.3.1. Location of case study site within Eastern Baltics (a) and naturally afforested former agricultural lands with *Populus tremula* (i), *Salix caprea* (ii), an overgrown abandoned farm in the study area (iii)(b)

3.2.2. Historical land-use assessment and land-use change trend

The interpretation of historical land use was based on available aerial photographs (Fig.3.2.). Hardcopy aerial photographs were scanned at high resolution (600 dpi) and georeferenced. Spatial assessment of land use changes was conducted by manually digitizing the aerial photographs using ESRI ArcGIS Desktop ArcMap 10.8.1 software. Three main land use types were distinguished: arable land, grassland, and forest. In addition, shrubs and overgrown agricultural land, forest clearing, and afforested agricultural land were mapped. During fieldwork, digitized plots were examined to verify boundary accuracy and classification of current land use types.

Fig.3.2. Fragment of aerial photo of the study area used to determine changes: (a) 1954, (b) 1978, and (c) 1999 grey-scale aerial photographs, (d) 2014 and (e) 2021 colour orthophotos

A systematic 100x100 m grid of points was generated across the case study area, and land use data for specific years were extracted from manually digitized maps at each point. The most prevalent land use change trajectories were subsequently identified (Table 3.1.). Between 1954 and 2014, the study area experienced significant land use transformations, which were categorized into the following dominant change scenarios: (1) conversion from arable land to grassland, (2) persistence of grassland, (3) conversion from arable land to forest, (4) conversion from grassland to forest.

Table 3.1.

Dominants land use change scenarios at the case study site based on spatial analysis

Grassland → forest
Shrubs and overgrown agricultural land → forest
Arable land → grassland
Grassland → shrubs and overgrown agricultural land → forest
Arable land → grassland → forest
Arable land → grassland → arable land

3.2.3. Soil description and analysis

The study area was conceptualized as a heterogeneous landscape composed of distinct land-use types. It was stratified into 34 land-use parcels, delineated based on historical field boundaries from 1954 and uniform vegetation patterns observed in 2021. Within each parcel, a random sampling point was selected for soil profile establishment, ensuring unbiased representation of soil characteristics across the landscape (Fig.3.3.f). A total of 34 soil profiles were examined across prevalent land-use scenarios: arable land to grassland (n=11), grassland to grassland (n=7), arable land to forest (n=7), and grassland to forest (n=9). For each profile, the following information was collected: WRB soil group (IUSS Working Group, 2022), location on the terrain, and vegetation cover. Additionally, soil samples were collected for further analysis in the laboratory. The samples were air-dried, sieved through a 2mm mesh (Tan, 2005).

Both physical and chemical analyses were performed, including the determination of soil texture (sand, silt, clay (%)) (van Reeuwijk, 1995), pH_{KCl} , total carbon (%) (Tan, 2005), total nitrogen (g kg^{-1}), exchangeable cations (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , K^{+}) (mg kg^{-1}) according to the standard methods used in ICP (International Co-operative Programme) Forest monitoring (Cools & De Vos, 2010).

3.2.4. Statistical analyses

To assess the differences between multiple groups of land use change scenarios, a nonparametric Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted due to the non-normal distribution of the data. The Kruskal-Wallis test is a rank-based method suitable for comparing more than two independent samples without the assumption of normality. Pairwise comparisons were performed following a significant Kruskal-Wallis test result to identify specific group differences. To control for multiple comparisons and reduce the risk of Type I errors, a Bonferroni correction was applied to the significance values.

3.3. Results

3.3.1. Land use change scenarios in marginal areas in Eastern Baltics

The analysis of land use dynamics in the study area from 1954 to 2021 reveals significant transformations across multiple land use types (Table 3.2., Fig.3.3.).

In 1954 (Fig.3.3.a), the landscape was predominantly characterized by grassland, which occupied 46.0% of the area, followed by arable land, which covered 33.2%. Forest accounted for only 9.9% of the area, while shrubs and overgrown agricultural land made up 10.9%.

By 1978 (Fig.3.3.b), significant shifts had occurred. Grassland expanded to 58.7%, while arable land sharply decreased to 5.2%. Forest cover more than doubled to 28.6%. Shrubs and overgrown agricultural land slightly declined to 7.5% m which could be explained by the fact that areas overgrown

24 years ago are now classified as forest. These changes suggest widespread grassland expansion and natural afforestation, with substantial abandonment of arable land. Small landscape elements and linear features began to appear along roads, while arable land predominantly remained near individual farmsteads.

Forest cover in 1999 continued to increase (Fig.3.3.c), reaching 49.9%, becoming the dominant land use type. Grassland significantly declined to 38.9%, while arable land further decreased to 1.4%. The 9.8% increase in shrubs and overgrown agricultural land suggests ongoing secondary succession, primarily driven by overgrowth from the forest edge. This also indicates a continued trend of natural afforestation and agricultural land abandonment, with a significant rise in the number of individual trees on agricultural land, further reflecting farmland abandonment.

Forest remained the dominant land use in 2014 (Fig.3.3.d), expanding to 60.5%. Grassland area dropped further to 23.3%, while arable land almost disappeared, covering just 0.008%. Shrubs and overgrown agricultural land decreased to 6.6%. Notably, forest clearing emerged for the first time, covering 9.1% of the area. This can be attributed to the fact that, within this period of 60 years, the trees reached their optimal cutting age. The afforested agricultural land, covering 0.4% of the area, along with forest clearing, reflects an increase in forest management activities.

As of 2021 (Fig.3.3.e), forest cover continued expanding to 67.5%, while grassland area continued to decrease, reaching 9.3%. Arable land showed an increase, reaching 6.4%. This could be attributed to agricultural subsidy, as several fields were registered as fallow land. Forest clearing decreased slightly to 7.7%, and afforested agricultural land significantly increased to 6.4%. Shrubs and overgrown agricultural land continued declining to 2.9%.

Table 3.2.

Occupied area (%) across different land use types in the study area (1954-2021)

Land use type	1954	1978	1999	2014	2021
	Area (%)				
Arable land	33.2	5.2	1.4	0.008	6.4
Grassland	46.0	58.7	38.9	23.3	9.3
Shrubs and overgrown agricultural land	10.9	7.5	9.8	6.6	2.9
Forest land (sum)	9.9	28.6	49.9	70.0	81.6
Including woodland	9.9	28.6	49.9	60.5	67.5
Including forest clearing	–	–	–	9.1	7.7
Including afforested agricultural land	–	–	–	0.4	6.4

Fig.3.3. Land use types in the study area in the period from 1954 to 2021: 1954(a), 1978 (b), 1999(c), 2014(d), 2021(e), and parcels and soil sampling sites (f)

Arable land saw significant declines from 1954 to 1978, with smaller reductions until 1999 and a slight increase between 2014 and 2021. Grassland initially increased slightly from 1954 to 1978 but then sharply declined from 1978 to 1999, continuing to decrease through 2021. Forest area experienced steady growth throughout all periods, with the most significant expansion from 1978 to 1999, continuing into 2021. Forest clearing emerged between 1999 and 2014, with a slight decrease from 2014 to 2021. Afforested agricultural land appeared between 1999 and 2014, with notable growth from 2014 to 2021. Shrubs and overgrown agricultural land decreased from 1954 to 1978, increased slightly from 1978 to 1999, and then declined again through 2021 (Table 3.3.).

Table 3.3.

Changes in studied area (317.9 ha) within each land use type (1954–2021)
(*blue* -represents the loss of area, *red* – the gain of area)

Land use type	Changes in area (ha)					
	1954-1978	1978-1999	1999-2014	2014-2021	1954-2014	1954-2021
Arable land	-89.1	-12.0	-4.4	+20.2	-105.5	-85.3
Grassland	+40.3	-62.9	-49.7	-44.7	-72.3	-117.0
Shrubs and overgrown agricultural land	-10.6	+7.2	-10.0	-12.0	-13.4	-25.4
Forest land (sum)	+59.4	+67.8	+64.0	+36.5	+160.8	+183.0
Including woodland	+59.4	+67.8	+33.7	+22.2	+160.8	+183.0
Including forest clearing	-	-	+28.9	-4.6	-	-
Including afforested agricultural land	-	-	+1.4	+18.9	-	-

3.3.2. Soil factors driving secondary succession across land use types

The description of the main parameters in the land use change scenarios is summarized in Table 3.4. In the arable land to grassland scenario, the dominant soil groups are Phaeozems, Stagnosols, and Luvisols, with soil textures ranging from loam to sandy loam. The soil profile is typically found on middle slopes. The transition to grassland is associated with tree species like *Alnus incana* and *Salix caprea*, which are commonly found in this region.

In the grassland to grassland scenario, the dominant soil groups are Luvisols and Cambisols, with sandy loam and sandy clay loam textures. The soil profile is located on middle slopes. The presence of species like *Salix caprea* and *Betula pendula* suggests the potential for early-stage forest development.

In the arable land to forest scenario, the dominant soil groups are Stagnosols and Phaeozems, with sandy loam and loam textures. These soils are mainly found in interhill drainless depressions, where moisture retention supports forest regeneration. Tree species such as *Alnus incana*, *Betula pendula*, and *Picea abies* dominate the forest.

Table 3.4.

Description of main parameters in land use change scenarios
 (CR- hill top, MS – middle slope, LS – lower slope, BI - interhill drainless depression) (n=34)

Scenarios	Soil group (WRB 2022)	Soil texture	Location on the terrain	Dominant tree species
Arable land- grassland (n=11)	Phaeozems (n=4)	Loam (n=5)	MS (n=5)	<i>Alnus incana</i> (n=7)
	Stagnosols (n=4)	Sandy loam (n=3)	CR (n=3)	<i>Salix caprea</i> (n=3)
	Luvisols (n=3)	Sandy clay loam (n=2)	LS (n=2)	<i>Picea abies</i> (n=1)
		Clay loam (n=1)	BI (n=1)	
Grassland-grassland (n=7)	Luvisols (n=3)	Sandy loam (n=4)	MS (n=5)	<i>Salix caprea</i> (n=3)
	Cambisols (n=2)	Sandy clay loam (n=3)	BI (n=1)	<i>Betula pendula</i> (n=2)
	Retisols (n=1)		LS (n=1)	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i> (n=1)
	Phaeozems (n=1)			<i>Quercus robur</i> (n=1)
Arable land – forest (n=7)	Stagnosols (n=3)	Sandy loam (n=3)	BI (n=5)	<i>Alnus incana</i> (n=4)
	Phaeozems (n=2)	Loam (n=3)	MS (n=1)	<i>Betula pendula</i> (n=1)
	Retisols (n=1)	Sandy clay loam (n=1)	CR (n=1)	<i>Picea abies</i> (n=1)
	Luvisols (n=1)			<i>Salix caprea</i> (n=1)
Grassland – forest (n=9)	Phaeozems (n=5)	Sandy loam (n=4)	BI (n=3)	<i>Alnus incana</i> (n=6)
	Luvisols (n=2)	Loam (n=3)	MS (n=2)	<i>Populus tremula</i> (n=1)
	Retisols (n=1)	Sandy clay loam (n=1)	CR (n=2)	<i>Betula pendula</i> (n=1)
	Cambisols (n=1)	Clay loam (n=1)	LS (n=2)	<i>Salix caprea</i> (n=1)

Table 3.5.

The soil properties of the upper layer in diverse land use scenarios (n=34)

Soil properties	Land use change scenarios				
		Arable land - grassland (n=11)	Grassland- grassland (n=7)	Arable land – forest (n=7)	Grassland – forest (n=9)
pH_{KCl} value	Mean	6.0*	5.9	4.7*	5.4
	SD	1.0	0.9	0.8	0.8
	Min	4.6	4.6	4.1	4.3
	Max	7.4	7.2	5.8	6.7
C_{TOC}, %	Mean	2.2	2.2	1.7	3.1
	SD	0.9	0.9	0.6	2.8
	Min	1.1	1.1	1.1	1.2
	Max	3.7	3.6	2.6	8.6
N_{TN}, mg kg⁻¹	Mean	0.8	0.9	0.7	1.2
	SD	0.3	0.2	0.1	1.1
	Min	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.5
	Max	1.3	1.3	0.9	3.6
Mg²⁺, mg kg⁻¹	Mean	192.2	211.7	127.6	285.9
	SD	77.8	126.0	50.9	328.4
	Min	62.1	125.5	50.0	71.4
	Max	322.1	485.3	183.0	885.4
K⁺, mg kg⁻¹	Mean	57.8	86.4	44.4	44.3
	SD	35.8	43.6	23.4	14.6
	Min	13.3	24.6	21.8	24.2
	Max	137.1	139.6	81.8	68.7
Ca²⁺, mg kg⁻¹	Mean	2146.6	1971.4	1080.2	2960.1
	SD	1286.6	941.6	592.5	3565.6
	Min	518.5	818.4	475.3	737.2
	Max	4552.3	3464.6	1974.2	9265.7
Thickness of A horizon, cm	Mean	28.5	26.9	34.7	31.1
	SD	13.5	18.1	12.8	7.3
	Min	5.0	12.0	27.0	25.0
	Max	55.0	65.0	63.0	50.0
Sand particles, %	Mean	51.5	55.0	51.9	51.8
	SD	8.4	4.6	6.1	11.3
	Min	38.0	47.0	45.0	28.0
	Max	67.0	61.0	60.0	70.0
Silt particles, %	Mean	28.8	25.6	29.0	29.9
	SD	8.4	2.9	4.0	7.2
	Min	15.0	22.0	22.0	14.0
	Max	46.0	31.0	34.0	41.0
Clay particles, %	Mean	19.7	19.4	19.1	18.3
	SD	3.5	5.3	4.4	7.3
	Min	15.0	13.0	13.0	5.0
	Max	27.0	29.0	25.0	31.0

* - The statistically significant ($p < 0,05$) difference between land use change scenarios

In the grassland to forest scenario, the dominant soil groups are Phaeozems and Luvisols, with sandy loam and loam textures. These soils are found in interhill drainless depressions, as well as on top, middle, and lower slopes. The dominant tree species in the forest at the research site is *Alnus incana*.

The results presented in Table 3.5. outline the soil properties of the upper layer across different land use scenarios. The arable land to grassland scenario exhibited the highest pH_{KCl} among the scenarios, while the arable land to forest scenario showed significantly lower pH_{KCl} , indicating acidification. The Kruskal-Wallis test confirmed a statistically significant difference in pH_{KCl} between these scenarios, with a test statistic of 12.968 (SE = 4.814) and a standard test statistic of 2.693. The raw significance was 0.007, and after Bonferroni correction, the adjusted significance was 0.042.

Organic carbon content (C_{TOC}) and nitrogen content (N_{TN}) were highest in the grassland to forest scenario, suggesting greater organic matter accumulation. In contrast, the arable land to forest scenario had the lowest C_{TOC} and N_{TN} values, reflecting lower organic matter content.

Regarding exchangeable cations, magnesium and calcium was highest in the grassland to forest scenario, while potassium was more prominent in grassland to grassland. Whereas the lowest values for all three cations (Mg^{2+} , K^+ , Ca^{2+}) were observed in the arable land to forest scenario, indicating lower nutrient availability.

The arable land to forest scenario also displayed the thickest A horizon, while the grassland to grassland scenario had the thinnest. Particle size distribution remained consistent across all scenarios, with sand particles being slightly more prevalent in grassland to grassland, and silt and clay content varying minimally.

3.4. Conclusions

This study highlights the significant land use changes that have occurred in the case study area over several decades, largely driven by the extensification of land use, natural afforestation, and agricultural land abandonment. The findings demonstrate a clear trend of grassland and arable land transitioning to forest cover, particularly between 1978 and 1999, with forest cover significantly increasing by 2021. Forest management activities, including forest clearing and afforestation of agricultural land, have become more prominent in recent years. Notably, the afforestation of agricultural lands with not common tree species, such as *Picea abies*, raises concerns about potential alterations to soil chemical properties and microbial activity, emphasizing the need for political regulation regarding afforestation practices.

Soil properties in the study area are strongly influenced by the dominant soil groups—Phaeozems, Stagnosols, and Luvisols—coupled with topographic factors, where grasslands are primarily found at higher elevations and forests in lower elevations and interhill depressions. The study also identified distinct differences in soil properties between land use transitions, particularly the acidification and nutrient reduction associated with forest establishment on former arable land. In contrast, grassland-to-forest transitions contributed to greater organic matter accumulation and nutrient enrichment.

Despite the observed trends, the heavy textural composition of the soils in the region suggests a lower sensitivity to changes between some land use scenarios. The only significant statistical difference observed was in soil pH between the arable land to grassland and arable land to forest transitions. Further studies with larger sample sizes are recommended to deepen our understanding of these dynamics and inform more targeted land management strategies. This research highlights the critical role of biophysical factors in managing land use changes, particularly in regions with widespread agricultural land abandonment, as observed in the current case study. Understanding the interplay between these factors and land use transitions, such as natural afforestation and soil property shifts, is essential for developing effective land management strategies and informed policy decisions.

4. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. In order to achieve the aims of the EU agricultural policy and improve the management of agricultural lands, it is preferable to base the land use analysis on data on land use in specific landscape types or natural areas, as land use trends and its driving forces differs by the landscape type.
2. Currently, EU and national regulations or CAP eco-schemes do not provide the climate-neutral use of peat soils. In the aspect of biological diversity, grasslands should be maintained, but on the other hand – in the aspect of reduction of the GHG emissions, it is recommended to afforest deep peat soils.
3. Data actualisation, harmonization and development of new soil mapping and providing of related information is urgently needed to implement data-driven management of agricultural lands. Special attention should be paid to the spatial distribution of organic soils.
4. National policies and individual sectors (e.g. agriculture and forestry) regards to agricultural land abandonment - differs. In order to provide common or unified policy – it is recommended to be based on the approach of ecosystem services, it is necessary to take into account many factors: maintenance of biological diversity, reduction of GHG emissions, soil health and landscape as a resource.

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